

CTH3 (Bili Mukthi), a white-grained, cold- and blast (BI)-tolerant rice for southern Karnataka, India

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About 0.3 million ha of rice is cultivated in southern Karnataka under both canal- and reservoir-irrigated conditions. Canal-irrigated rice is planted during Jun-Jul because of the assured, regulated release of stored water. But reservoir-fed rice can be planted only after the reservoirs are full. This delay normally leads to late planting — sometimes not until September.

Even the very early-maturing recommended varieties, when planted after mid-August, flower during November (winter) and do not perform well. For such conditions, the only suitable variety that has been recently released is Mukthi (CTH1), a red-grained rice that few farmers prefer.

CTH3, a new selection from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery planted at Bangalore during 1983 winter, was multiplied for seed during 1984 and tested in three locations within Karnataka. It can meet the demand for a white-grained, cold- and BI-tolerant variety, and can supplement Mukthi over large areas in the reservoir-irrigated winter rice belt.

CTH3 was obtained from IR9202-25-1-3, derived from TR2053-521-1-1/K116/KN-1B-361-1-8-6-9-1. The selection is 95 cm high, has medium bold grains, moderate tillering, and grows normally from germination to maturity in any season because of its cold and BI tolerance and photoperiod insensitivity.

It yielded OS-5.0 t grain/ha during normal season and 0.6 to 1.9 t grain/ha during winter compared with 0.02-1.1 t/ha for best checks Mangala and CH2 (both white-grained) under winter conditions.

The table summarizes the performance of CTH3 for 6 yr at Bangalore. Its leaf BI score of 2 and 2% neck BI are better than the 7 and 5% for susceptible variety Halubblu. The performance of CTH3 at

Performance of cold-tolerant varieties from 2 plantings (Sep, Oct) at Bangalore, India, 1985-86 to 1990-91.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)												Total mean (t/ha)	Increase (%)over CH2	Blast			
	1985-86		1986-87		1987-88	1988-89		1989-90		1990-91		Mean			Sep	Oct	Leaf ^a	Neck (%)
	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct	Sep	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct							
CTH1	2.3	1.7	4.9	3.5	3.9	1.3	1.5	1.4	2.0	1.4	2.6	2.0	2.3	107	2	0		
CTH3	1.2	0.6	5.0	1.9	1.8	0.5	0.9	1.8	1.0	0.7	1.9	1.0	1.5	28	2	2		
Checks																		
Mangala	0.3	0.1	3.6	0.7	1.4	0.5	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.6	1.3	0.4	0.8	—	2	2.4		
CH2	1.3	1.1	3.6	0.5	2.2	0.4	—	1.0	0.7	0.6	1.5	0.7	1.1		2	1.5		
LSD	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1	ns	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2	—	—	—					
CV (%)	14.9	16.1	13.7	14.2	19.2	—	27.5	21.4	23.5	19.4	—	—	—					

^aScored using Standard evaluation system for rice (0-9).

Bangalore, Mandya, and Mudigere during 1985-91 and on private farms in Mysore district has confirmed its superiority in winter and high degree of BI tolerance.

It is now approved for farm trials in Karnataka in the hill zone and is spreading from farmer to farmer in Mysore district under the name Bili Mukthi. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed

TKM10, a new higher yielding rice for semidry conditions

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Rice is cultivated on about 45,000 ha under semidry conditions (rainfed lowland-subsequently irrigated) in Chengalpattu MGR district of Tamil Nadu, India.

Table 1. Overall yield performance of TKM10.

Trial	no.	Yield (t/ha)	
		TKM10	TKM1
Research Station			
Tirur	4	1.9	1.1
Adaptive research trial			
October 1989-90	28	2.0	1.7
Adaptive research trial			
October 1990-91	19	3.8	2.7
Mean		2.6	1.8

Table 2. Drought score at RSS, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, 1989-91.

Entry	Parentage	1989-90		1990-91	
		Tolerance	Recovery	Tolerance	Recovery
TKM 10	CO 31/C22	1	1	1	1
IR20	IR262/TKM6	5	5	3	5
TKM1	Pisini (local selection)	1	1	1	1
CO 31	GEB24/ <i>O. perennis</i>	1	1	1	1
IET 1444	TN1/CO 29	5	3	5	3
TKMY	TKM7/IR8	3	3	3	1

^aScored using SES.

TKM1, a local genotype released 30 yr ago as a pureline variety from Pisini, was previously the only suitable variety for this environment.

We initiated breeding work to develop a drought-tolerant, high-yielding semidry rice. This work resulted in the identification of elite culture TM8602, a hybrid derivative of the cross CO 31/C22, which was released as TKM 10. This culture is a semitall plant with nonlodging culms.

Trials conducted in both RRS and farmers' fields revealed the high-yielding potential of this genotype compared with check TKM1. TKM10 averaged 2.6 t grain/ha (Table 1) with a maximum yield of 5.2 t/ha recorded in a trial plot that received enough rainfall during sowing and vegetative and reproductive phases.

TKM10 matures in 135 d under direct seeding. Its seedlings, along with checks, were assessed for drought tolerance during the vegetative phase in 1989-90 and 1990-

91. Plants were scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) after 20 continuous drought days under field conditions. TKM10, CO 31, and TKM1 showed only slight tip drying. These three rice types recovered quickly and established well when the plots were irrigated, while others showed

various degrees of drought tolerance and recovery (Table 2).

TKM10 has medium slender, white grains. Its cooking quality is good. Consumers prefer it because it is highly suitable as both raw and parboiled rice.

It is moderately resistant to gall midge, green leafhopper, and leafhopper

under field conditions and brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and leafhopper under artificial conditions.

It was moderately resistant to blast (under field and artificial screening), brown leaf spot, and sheath rot. It was moderately susceptible to rice tungro virus. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Physiology and plant nutrition

Leaf thickness affects the estimation of leaf N using a chlorophyll meter

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Several studies recently published in international journals evaluated the use of a chlorophyll meter to estimate rice leaf N concentration with the goal of predicting the need for fertilizer-N topdressing. The accuracy of this estimation, however, was influenced by the stage of plant development, genotype, and the number of meter readings taken on an individual leaf blade. We conducted this study to determine how many point-readings were sufficient to accurately estimate the N concentration of an individual leaf and whether leaf thickness affected the estimation.

We used a chlorophyll meter (Minolta SPAD-502) to determine the SPAD

values of 20 intact IR50 flag leaves at flowering in the greenhouse. Nine SPAD readings were taken at 30-mm intervals from the base to the tip of each leaf blade. All measurements were made in the leaf margin on one side of the midrib. We then measured leaf area and determined the dry weight after oven-drying the leaves at 70°C. Specific leaf weight (SLW), which reflects leaf thickness, was calculated as the ratio of dry weight to leaf area. Leaf N concentration was determined by standard microkjeldahl digestion and distillation.

In a field study in the 1992 dry season, we took SPAD readings on the 12 uppermost fully expanded leaves at midtillering of IR72. For each leaf, mean SPAD value represented the average of three SPAD readings taken around the midpoint of the blade, 30 mm apart, on one side of the midrib. Leaf N and SLW were determined as in the greenhouse study.

Values of SPAD were closely related to leaf N concentration (see table). Increasing the number of readings from one at the middle of the blade to three that bracketed the midpoint of the leaf resulted in a significant increase in the coefficient of determination (r^2). Further increases in readings per leaf blade did not increase r^2 . Therefore, only three SPAD readings around the midpoint on one side of the midrib can provide a reasonable estimate of leaf N concentration.

Six of the 20 flag leaves that were sampled in the greenhouse had 3.72% N (± 0.04 SD), although SPAD values varied from 44.5 to 49.0. The SPAD values were positively related to SLW (see figure), indicating that leaf thickness and N concentration influence the SPAD reading. Multiple linear regression also revealed that both SPAD values and

Relationship between leaf N concentration and mean SPAD values of individual leaves as influenced by the number of SPAD readings taken around the midpoint of each leaf blade (simple regression), and the significant effect of specific leaf weight (SLW) on this relationship in the greenhouse and field studies (multiple regression).^a

Readings/leaf	Simple/multiple regression	r^2	R^2
Greenhouse (n = 20)			
1	N% = -0.49 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.69***	
3	N% = -0.75 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.81***	
5	N% = -0.84 + 0.10 (SPAD)	0.79***	
7	N% = -0.72 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.75***	
9	N% = -0.69 + 0.09 (SPAD)	0.76***	
3	N% = -0.04 + 0.10 (SPAD) - 0.21 (SLW)		0.86***
Field (n = 72)			
3	N% = -0.30 + 0.11 (SPAD)	0.74***	
3	N% = 0.54 + 0.11 (SPAD) - 0.21 (SLW)		0.78***

^a *** = significant at P<0.001.

Relationship between specific leaf weight (SLW) and SPAD values of 6 leaves with similar N concentration in a greenhouse study. ** = significant at P < 0.01.